

Interaction studies of alcohols with aqueous anionic surfactants at different temperatures

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Abstract : The effect of monohydric, short chain alcohols, 1-propanol and 1-butanol on the micellar behavior of anionic surfactants, sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) and sodium dodecylbenzene sulfonate (SDBS) was investigated using experimental densities, ρ , and speed of sound, u , data measured at 298.15, 303.15 and 308.15 K. Apparent molar volumes (Φ_v), partial molar volumes (Φ_v^0), transfer volume ($\Phi_{v(tr)}^0$), partial molar isobaric expansibilities (Φ_E^0) and isentropic compressibility (κ_s) were calculated to elucidate the interactions prevailing in the studied aqueous-surfactant-alcohol systems. Further, ^1H NMR chemical shift measurements in micelle solutions of SDS and SDBS containing 1-butanol have also been carried out to elucidate the site for preferential solubilization of alcohol in the studied anionic surfactants. The results obtained are compared with the conclusions drawn from the thermodynamic measurements.

Keywords : Surfactants, partial molar volume, isentropic compressibility, ^1H NMR studies.

Introduction

The effect of organic solvents like alcohols on micellization of anionic surfactants is of much interest^{1,2} and the micellar composition of aqueous surfactant-alcohol systems has been extensively studied³⁻⁸. Micellization is likely to undergo a significant change in the presence of such additives⁹⁻¹¹. The studies of micellization of surfactant molecules under different experimental conditions continue to be of great interest, because of their wide range of industrial applications and also they play very important role in the preparation of micro emulsions. The short chain alcohols are solubilized mainly in the aqueous phase and affect the micellization process by modifying the solvent properties. Further, these alcohols in low concentration promote micellization probably by residing at the micellar surface and reducing the micelle surface area per head group, which in turn reduce the unfavorable water hydrocarbon contacts. At higher concentrations these alcohols destabilize micelles by displacing water from the surface, therefore decreasing its effective dielectric constant, increasing head group repulsions, and disrupting surfactant packing¹².

This paper is in continuation of my study on the effect of alcohols on the micellization behavior of anionic surfactants^{12,13}. The surfactants taken for the present study are sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS); which is much investi-

gated and is a good representative of anionic surfactants whereas, the solution properties of sodium dodecylbenzene sulfonate (SDBS) have not been critically examined although several papers are available in the literature¹⁴⁻¹⁷. While the reports on the interaction of SDS with alcohols are considerable^{1,5,9} that with SDBS is quite limited¹³.

Thus, keeping these considerations, the density, ρ and speed of sound, u have been measured for alcohols, 1-propanol and 1-butanol in 0.1 mol kg⁻¹ aqueous solution of SDS and SDBS at 298.15, 303.15 and 308.15 K to evaluate various parameters. Apart from these, ^1H NMR studies have also been carried out for the present surfactant - 1-butanol systems the results of which are interpreted in terms of the approximate location of the alcohols in the micellar aggregates. An elaborate and critical study of the micellization and interfacial properties of SDS and SDBS and its interaction with *n*-alcohols has been made. An emphasis has been given to the solutions of SDBS because an exhaustive survey of literature reveals that no one has reported such extensive study of aqueous micelle solution of SDBS above the CMC containing monohydric short chain alcohols using thermodynamic properties.

Results and discussion

The experimental data of density and speed of sound

for 1-propanol and 1-butanol at 298.15, 303.15 and 308.15 K are presented in Table 1, whereas experimentally measured densities and speeds of sound of alcohols, 1-pro-

utilized to obtain partial molar volumes (Φ_v^0), transfer volume ($\Phi_{v(tr)}^0$) and partial molar isobaric expansibilities (Φ_E^0) in the following relations

Table 1. Experimental values of density (ρ) and speed of sound (u) of pure alcohols at different temperatures

Alcohols	T (K)	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻³)	u (m s ⁻¹)
1-Propanol	298.15	0.799890	1206.4
	303.15	0.799532	1191.11
	308.15	0.791763	1172.5
1-Butanol	298.15	0.806172	1240.6
	303.15	0.803155	1226.5
	308.15	0.798420	1207.1

panol and 1-butanol in aqueous SDS and SDBS solutions at 298.15, 303.15 and 308.15 K and atmospheric pressure are reported in Table 2. Density values were used to obtain the apparent molar volumes (Φ_v) which in turn are

$$\Phi_v = \frac{1000 (\rho_0 - \rho)}{m\rho\rho_0} + \frac{M}{\rho} \quad (1)$$

$$\Phi_v = \Phi_v^0 + S_v m \quad (2)$$

$$\Phi_{v(tr)}^0 = \Phi_v^0 \text{ (in aqueous surfactant)} - \Phi_v^0 \text{ (in water)} \quad (3)$$

where, ρ_0 , ρ , M and m are, respectively, the density of the pure solvent (aqueous surfactant), density of solution (aqueous surfactant + alcohol) the molar mass of the solute and the molality of the solute (alcohols) in mol kg⁻¹. Φ_v^0 (in water) is the partial molar volume of the alcohols in water and its values for 1-propanol and 1-butanol at 298.15 K have been taken from the literature¹⁸.

Further, the values of Φ_v^0 have been fitted with least

Table 2. Experimental values of densities (ρ) and speed of sound (u) of alcohols in 0.01 mol kg⁻¹ aqueous surfactant solutions at different temperatures

m (mol kg ⁻¹)	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻³)			u (m s ⁻¹)		
	298.15	303.15	308.15	298.15	303.15	308.15
SDS + 1-propanol						
0.0000	1.000990	0.999450	0.997750	1498.40	1509.50	1519.30
0.0200	1.000770	0.999228	0.997524	1499.20	1510.21	1519.91
0.0674	1.000247	0.998697	0.996986	1501.08	1511.87	1521.31
0.1210	0.999650	0.998091	0.996373	1503.18	1513.73	1522.87
0.1501	0.999324	0.997762	0.996038	1504.30	1514.76	1523.68
0.2000	0.998760	0.997187	0.995456	1506.24	1516.49	1525.05
0.2501	0.998190	0.996610	0.994870	1508.14	1518.23	1526.39
0.3068	0.997540	0.995945	0.994200	1510.29	1520.18	1527.85
SDS + 1-butanol						
0.0000	1.000990	0.999450	0.997750	1498.40	1509.50	1519.30
0.0663	1.000135	0.998587	0.996879	1500.69	1511.44	1520.84
0.1056	0.999630	0.998078	0.996365	1502.02	1512.57	1521.75
0.1501	0.999061	0.997505	0.995786	1503.51	1513.83	1522.76
0.2000	0.998422	0.996861	0.995137	1505.15	1515.25	1523.90
0.2503	0.997784	0.996219	0.994490	1506.77	1516.60	1524.98
0.3003	0.997148	0.995580	0.993844	1508.34	1518.00	1526.07
0.3404	0.996641	0.995070	0.993330	1509.60	1519.05	1526.96
SDBS + 1-propanol						
0.0000	1.0033	1.00175	1.000000	1502.50	1513.50	1523.00
0.0880	1.002397	1.000820	0.999046	1506.06	1516.74	1525.83
0.1216	1.002054	1.000465	0.998683	1507.38	1517.93	1526.87
0.1601	1.001661	1.000058	0.998266	1508.89	1519.30	1528.08

Table-2 (contd)

0.2112	1.001141	0.999520	0.997714	1510.90	1521.10	1529.68
0.2604	1.000642	0.999000	0.997185	1512.81	1522.84	1531.15
0.3211	1.000030	0.998365	0.996530	1515.11	1524.82	1532.95
0.4416	0.998820	0.997100	0.995236	1519.60	1528.53	1536.45
SDBS + 1-butanol						
0.0000	1.0033	1.00175	1.000000	1502.50	1513.5	1523.00
0.0904	1.002151	1.000589	0.998825	1506.06	1516.62	1525.50
0.1201	1.001774	1.000207	0.998439	1507.20	1517.60	1526.30
0.1779	1.00104	0.999465	0.997691	1509.40	1519.47	1527.83
0.2213	1.000490	0.998909	0.997129	1510.96	1520.77	1528.90
0.2603	0.999995	0.998408	0.996623	1512.41	1521.96	1529.84
0.3110	0.999351	0.997756	0.995969	1514.20	1523.40	1531.04
0.3639	0.998683	0.997078	0.995288	1516.00	1524.93	1532.28

square method to the following equation used by Chalikian *et al.*¹⁹,

$$\Phi_v^0 = a + bT + cT^2 \quad (4)$$

where a , b and c are the constants and T is the temperature. The differentiation of eq. (4) with respect to temperature leads to the partial molar isobaric expansibility, Φ_E^0 ,

$$\Phi_E^0 = (\partial\Phi_v^0/\partial T)_p = b + 2cT \quad (5)$$

The differentiation of eq. (5) yields :

$$(\partial c_p^0/\partial p)_T = -T(\partial^2\Phi_v^0/\partial T^2)_p = -2cT \quad (6)$$

where c_p^0 is the heat capacity of the solute at infinite dilution. The sign of eq. (6) provides quantitative information on structure-making or breaking ability of a solute in aqueous solution²⁰. The values of Φ_v^0 , S_v , Φ_v^0 (in water), $\Phi_{v(tr)}^0$ and Φ_E^0 values at different temperatures are summarized in Table 3.

The isentropic compressibility, κ_s , of the solution can be obtained by the Newton-Laplace equation,

$$\kappa_s = 1/u^2\rho \quad (7)$$

The ¹H NMR chemical shift studies of solutions containing 0.10 mol kg⁻¹ SDS or SDBS and different concentrations of 1-butanol has been done. The site for preferential solubilization of alcohols in the anionic surfactant solutions have been interpreted from the spectral analysis.

In case of aqueous SDS solutions, below the critical micelle concentration the value of Φ_v increases slightly with $m^{1/2}$ and is around 237 cm³ mol⁻¹ at 298.15 K²¹. Whereas, in case of SDBS, Φ_v vs $m^{1/2}$, plot show increasing trend with increase in concentration and temperature. A large increase occurs at low concentrations and a small but well defined break is observed at higher concentrations^{13,15}. This was explained by a decrease of

Table 3. Fit coefficients of the variation of Φ_v at 0.1 mol kg⁻¹ surfactant concentration at different temperatures for aqueous-surfactant-alcohol solutions

T (K)	$\Phi_v^0 \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$S_v \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻² L)	$\Phi_{v(water)}^0 \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\Phi_{v(tr)}^0 \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\Phi_E^0 \times 10^7$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
SDS + 1-propanol					
298.15	71.0220	1.4764	70.8 ^a	0.22	0.347
303.15	71.2144	1.6198	-	-	0.422
308.15	71.4445	1.5722	-	-	0.497
SDS + 1-butanol					
298.15	86.9903	0.4111	86.5 ^a	0.49	0.379
303.15	87.1867	0.3263	-	-	0.406
308.15	87.3965	0.3049	-	-	1.652
SDBS + 1-propanol					
298.15	70.2560	0.1770	70.8 ^a	-0.55	0.728
303.15	70.6108	0.4071	-	-	0.691

Table 3 (contd.)

308 15	70 9467	0 3933			0 653
			SDBS + 1 butanol		
298 15	86 6757	0 7053	86 5 ^a	0 17	0 361
303 15	86 8807	0 7692		-	0 459
308 15	87 1351	0 6197		-	0 558

^aRef 18

counter ion binding to the micelles which leads to increase intermicellar repulsive interaction. This repulsion favors a growth in micelle size at lower molar concentration in order to increase the intermicellar distances and to reduce the mutual repulsion. These results indicate that SDBS micelles apparently undergo a transition, probably sphere-to-rod at $\approx 0.15 \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$. According to Allaudin *et al.*¹⁵ the increase of Φ_v of aqueous solutions of SDBS during transition in SDBS micelles can lead to conclude that the counter ions of SDBS aggregates may be tightly bound and larger changes in coulombic and structural hydration arise during the transition. The plots of Φ_v vs molality of 1-propanol or 1-butanol in aqueous SDS and SDBS at different surfactant concentrations and temperatures are plotted in Fig. 1. It can be seen from Fig. 1, that Φ_v values are large positive for both the studied aqueous surfactant-alcohol systems, indicating the presence of strong surfactant-alcohol interactions. In solutions containing 1-propanol or 1-butanol the variations of Φ_v of studied alcohols are almost linear. The partial molar volumes Φ_v^0 at infinite dilution of the alcohols in aqueous micelle solution were determined by extrapolating the corresponding concentration dependence of the apparent molar volume to infinite dilution using the least squares method. The partial molar volume of a solute Φ_v^0 reflects the true volume of the solute and the volume change arising from the solute-solvent interactions. It means that the change in Φ_v^0 at different surfactant concentration and temperature should reflect the changes occurring in its environment in the micellar system. The parameter S_v provides information regarding solute-solute interactions. A perusal of Table 3 reveals that the values of Φ_v^0 are positive and they increase with the rise in temperature for the studied alcohols suggesting strong solute-solvent interactions. The value of Φ_v^0 for 1-propanol and 1-butanol in aqueous SDS or SDBS (0.1 mol kg^{-1}) solutions show that

there is a significant difference between Φ_v^0 for both the alcohols and in aqueous data, indicating that the alcohol molecules are partly solubilized in the micelle solution of studied surfactants. The positive sign of S_v indicates the interaction between the solute species is strong. According to Hoiland *et al.*⁵ the partial molar volumes of the alcohols in the micellar state are additive with a CH_2 group contribution of $17.1 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in non aqueous solvents. Φ_v^0 values for SDS-1-butanol system agree very well with the literature values ($87.27 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for 0.13 mol kg^{-1} aqueous SDS and $87.61 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for 0.16 mol kg^{-1} aqueous SDS solution)²². No data could be found for the studied SDBS-alcohol solutions on studied thermodynamic properties for comparison. The partial apparent molar properties of transfer, $\Phi_{v(\text{tr})}^0$, provide qualitative as well as quantitative information regarding solute-co solvent interactions without taking into account the effects of solute-solute interactions. The $\Phi_{v(\text{tr})}^0$ values at 298.15 K are summarized in Table 3. A perusal of Table 3 indicates that Φ_v^0 of alcohols in aqueous surfactants are greater than those in pure water, i.e. $\Phi_{v(\text{tr})}^0$ values are positive for all the studied systems and increase with increase in surfactant concentration. Exception is found in SDBS-1-propanol system where $\Phi_{v(\text{tr})}^0$ value is negative. The limiting partial molar isobaric expansibility, Φ_E^0 , is considered a useful measure of solute-solvent interactions present in the solution. Φ_E^0 values provide information regarding the size of the solute and its hydrophobicity. It can be seen from Table 3 that in case of SDS, 1-propanol (molar mass = $60.096 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$) and 1-butanol (molar mass = $74.1228 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$) have Φ_E^0 values almost equal at 298.15 and 303.15 K. However, Φ_E^0 values for 1-butanol in SDBS show lower values than that of 1-propanol at all the studied temperatures. The negative sign of $(\partial c_p^0 / \partial p)_T$ from eq. (6), signifies the structure-breaking and the positive sign represents struc-

Fig. 1. Plots of apparent molar volumes of alcohols in (a) SDS + 1-propanol, (b) SDS + 1-butanol, (c) SDBS + 1-propanol and (d) SDBS + 1-butanol at (■) 298.15, (●) 303.15 and (▲) 308.15 K.

ture-making capability of solute. Thus in the present investigation negative $(\partial c_p^0 / \partial p)_T$ values indicate that the studied alcohols act as structure-breaker in SDS and SDBS solutions. This is in agreement with the views suggested by Forland *et al.*²³. It was concluded that 1-propanol successively breaks down the micelles while 1-butanol shows a highly complex behavior on the structure of the micelle and can decrease or increase the size of the micelle aggregates, depending on the added alcohol concentration range²³.

The isentropic compressibility, κ_s , of aqueous solutions of SDS or SDBS containing 1-propanol or 1-butanol show decreasing trend at all the studied temperatures as in Fig. 2. The decrease in κ_s , suggests that it is incompletely transferred from the aqueous environment to the micelle or it is located near the surface of the micelle. According to Gonzalez-Perez *et al.*²⁴, hydration makes a negative contribution to the compressibility of a solute, as observed for monomeric surfactants as well as for simple electrolytes or their ions. In aqueous surfactant-alcohol system, the alcohols will partition between micelles and the aqueous solution. The short chain alcohols like propanol are solubilized mainly in the aqueous phase and affect the micellization process by modifying the solvent properties. Addition to these also results in a reduction of the size of the micelles but with a progressive breakdown of the surfactant aggregates at very high

Fig. 2. Plots of isentropic compressibility of alcohols in (a) SDS + 1-propanol, (b) SDS + 1-butanol, (c) SDBS + 1-propanol, and (d) SDBS + 1-butanol at (■) 298.15, (●) 303.15 and (▲) 308.15 K.

concentration²⁵. When the alcohol partitions between water and micellar pseudo phase, the fraction bound to the micelles replaces water molecules at the interface, leading to increased electrostatic repulsion between surfactant head groups³. The structural changes of the micelles indicate that 1-butanol solubilize in the micelle core in the high molality range, near the end of the solubility limit whereas propanol is too hydrophilic to do so. The results reported herein can be explained in terms of polar alcohols and/or aqueous SDS interaction, similar to that one found in surfactants above the critical micelle concentration²⁶.

The ¹H NMR techniques has been frequently used to evaluate the micellar morphology in single as well as in mixed micelles^{1,27}. The ¹H NMR chemical shift studies of solutions containing 0.10 mol kg⁻¹ SDS or SDBS and different concentrations of 1-butanol are reported in Tables 4 and 5 respectively. Typical spectra for 0.10 mol kg⁻¹

Table 4. Chemical shift (δ) of protons close to the head group of SDS in the presence and in the absence of 1-butanol in aqueous SDS at 295 K

m (mol kg ⁻¹)	SDS	Proton peaks in SDS micellar solutions (ppm)	
		peak c	peak d
0.10	0.0000	1.6129	3.9491
	0.0790	1.5707	3.9139
	0.2156	1.5525	3.9049
	0.5188	1.5476	3.8889

Table 5. Chemical shift (δ) of aryl protons of SDBS solutions in the presence and in the absence of 1-butanol in aqueous SDBS at 295 K

SDBS m (mol kg ⁻¹)	1-Butanol m (mol kg ⁻¹)	The variations range of aryl protons peaks (ppm)			
		a_1	a_2	b_1	b_2
0.10	0.0	7.5879	7.5679	6.9874	6.9677
	0.0832	7.5924	7.5763	7.0359	6.9740
	0.2391	7.6051	7.5865	7.0479	7.0069
	0.5932	7.6140	7.5942	7.0561	7.0008

studied aqueous surfactants and the assignment of various peaks in the absence and in the presence of 1-butanol are shown in Figs. 3 and 4 respectively. A careful inspection of various ¹H signals in the case of pure surfac-

tant solution and a shift in the position of these signals upon mixing 1-butanol helps to deduce the preferential solubilization sites of 1-butanol in aqueous SDS and SDBS solutions. A comparison of the chemical shift (δ) of the proton spectra of aqueous SDS solutions, (A) with that containing 0.2156 mol kg⁻¹ 1-butanol (B) in Fig. 3 clearly indicates the site for preferential solubilization of alcohol is close to the head group of micelle. This is apparent from the significant change in frequencies of the proton peaks (c and d) of Table 4. In SDS solutions at the studied concentration 0.10 mol kg⁻¹ peaks c and d show a small but up field shift with increase in concentration of 1-butanol. Since the change of chemical shift, caused by the aggregation of molecules is usually related to struc-

Fig. 3. ¹H NMR spectra in ppm at 295 K : (A) 0.1 mol kg⁻¹ SDS; (B) 0.2156 mol kg⁻¹ 1-butanol in 0.1 mol kg⁻¹ SDS in D₂O.

Fig. 4. Structure of SDS and ^1H NMR spectra in ppm at 295 K : (A) 0.1 mol kg $^{-1}$ SDS; (B) 0.2391 mol kg $^{-1}$ 1-butanol in 0.1 mol kg $^{-1}$ SDS in D_2O .

tural changes, the NMR experiments imply that the location of the added alcohols is in the interfacial region of a micellar aggregates. The results of the present study agree well with those reported by Reekmans *et al.*²⁸, where they studied ^{13}C NMR spectra of aqueous SDS-butanol/heptanol systems and concluded that chemical shift of $\text{C}_{10}\text{-C}_{12}$ of the SDS molecules are identical in the presence of the different added alcohol concentrations. However, the chemical shifts of the carbon atoms close to the head group of SDS change progressively upon addition of the alcohols and 1-butanol leads to a change of the chemical shift of carbon up to C_4 only²⁸. It has been observed that the short chain alcohols are preferentially solubilized in the palisade layer which contains the sur-

factant head groups, water and, in the case of ionic surfactants, counter ions²⁹. 1-Butanol is a water soluble alcohol and a considerable fraction (about 70%) of it remains in the aqueous phase²⁸. The three dimensional clusters of hydrogen bonds existing in the water and responsible for the hydrophobic force will be modified by the addition of 1-butanol. The overall effect of the alcohol is to break the structure of water. Typical spectra for 0.1 mol kg $^{-1}$ aqueous SDS and the assignment of various peaks in the presence and in the absence of 1-butanol (0.2391 mol kg $^{-1}$) are shown in Fig. 4. The chemical shift data for aryl protons (peaks a and b) show a small but consistent downfield shift with increasing concentrations of 1-butanol. For the sake of clarity, the probable

range of peaks a and b are presented in Table 5 as a_1 , a_2 and b_1 , b_2 respectively. A careful inspection of various ^1H signals in the case of pure surfactant solution and a shift in the position of these signals upon mixing 1-butanol helps to deduce the preferential solubilization sites of 1-butanol in aqueous SDBS solution. A comparison of the chemical shift (δ) of the proton spectra of aqueous SDBS solutions with that containing 1-butanol clearly indicates the site for preferential solubilization of alcohol is the aromatic ring of the micelle. This is apparent from the significant change in frequencies of the aryl proton peaks (peaks a and b) of Fig. 4. The chemical shift of methylene protons remains invariant. Similar observations were found in case of aqueous SDBS-1-pentanol systems¹³.

The peaks for the proton close to the tail of surfactants, SDS/SDBS are overlapping with the peaks due to methylene protons of 1-butanol which makes it difficult to interpret the shift in the position of protons close to the tail of studied surfactants. Apart from this the presence of a large number of protons (close to the tail of surfactants) appearing over a narrow range of chemical shift make it difficult to assign their exact position.

Experimental

The analytical grade 1-propanol and 1-butanol were distilled before use. The claimed purity for the chemicals was more than 99 mass%. SDS was obtained from HiMedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. (Mumbai) and was used as received whereas; SDBS of stated purity 88% was purchased from Acros Organics (New Jersey). It was purified by the method given in literature¹⁵. Deuterium oxide (Aldrich, 99.9% isotopic purity) was used without further purification as solvent in ^1H NMR studies. Deionized, double distilled water of conductance 1×10^{-6} mho cm^{-1} at 298.15 K was used for all measurements. Bidistilled water and alcohols were degassed by vacuum pump shortly before sample preparations. Solutions were prepared using an electronic balance (Afcoset-ER120A) with a precision of 0.0001 g. Measurements of the density and the speed of sound of pure liquids and their solutions were carried out using an Anton Paar DSA-5000 digital oscillating U-tube densimeter (Austria) pro-

vided with automatic viscosity correction and two integrated Pt 100 platinum thermometers. The temperature in the cell was regulated ± 0.001 K with a proportional temperature controller. The experimental details have been given in my previous communication¹³. The reproducibility of density and ultrasound measurements was $\pm 10^{-6}$ g cm^{-3} and $\pm 10^{-2}$ m s^{-1} , respectively, and the standard uncertainties³⁰ in density measurements were estimated to be $\pm 2 \times 10^{-3}$ kg m^{-3} , and for the speed of sound is ± 0.1 m s^{-1} .

In order to investigate the effect of alcohols on micellar phase ^1H NMR measurements were performed on Avance-II 400 NMR spectrometer at frequency 400.13 MHz. Deuterium oxide was used as the solvent instead of water to weaken the water signal for all solutions. The method depends on the ability of the alcohols to affect the chemical shift of different proton signals of the surfactant molecules. These chemical shifts were measured in the presence of 1-butanol as a function of alcohol concentrations. The chemical shift differences given on the δ scale in parts per million (ppm) of the applied frequency were only considered in this study.

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